

Delite Della Terra by Okuili ApS

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INTRODUCTION

According to the United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization, the meat in our diets leads to a release of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere during its production. Producing the annual beef diet of the average American, emits as much greenhouse gas as a car driven more than 1,800 miles. The beef production generates more than 100 times emissions than from producing mealworms [1][2]. Concerning this topic, our product was developed for the course Innovation in Future Food. We developed a product and a business plan for launching it to the market.

PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT

Our start-up, Okuili ApS, wants to increase the awareness and interest in eating insects as a food ingredient in Denmark. The strategy is making known dishes with insects as the main ingredient, to introduce slowly the concept of eating insects. Insects are of high nutritional value and consist of a high amount of protein. The first product, Delite Della Terra, has successfully been developed. Delite Della Terra is a tortellini-like, easy and fast to cook product. The dough is made of chickpea flour whereas the stuffing is made of insects (mealworms), herbs, cheeses and mushrooms, see figure 1.

Figure 1: The product and the packaging for Delite Della Terra

RESULTS AND CONCLUSION

The product was developed in the Food Department Laboratories. The proof of interest was tested with a survey to 174 potential consumers. The first variant with parsley was liked by 92 % of the consumers who tasted it; while, 79 % of the consumers liked the product with basil.

REFERENCES

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[2] A. van Huis, J. Van Itterbeeck, H. Klunder, E. Mertens, A. Halloran, G. Muir, and P. Vantomme, "Edible insects: future prospects for food and feed security," 2014.